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1 Boys and Girls gain in spatial, but not in mathematical ability after

2 Mental Rotation training in Primary education

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32

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36

37 **Conflict of Interest**

38 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

39

40 **Ethical approval**

41 The Ethics committee of the University (UNED) approved the study with written informed
42 consent from all participants. Written consent was obtained from them, in accordance with the
43 Declaration of Helsinki.

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Abstract

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Several studies have shown that spatial skills can be improved and are linked to mathematical reasoning. However, there are few studies that have evaluated the effect of Mental Rotation (MR) training on mathematical performance in children aged 6-8 years. One of the studies has shown a transfer towards a mathematical task, while the other has failed to demonstrate it. The present study investigated with children in 2nd grade of Primary Education the effect of training on MR, with 450 trials distributed across three sessions, as well as on mathematical competence. The results showed an improvement in this spatial skill in the experimental group in relation to the control ($\eta_p^2 = .10$). There were no differences between sexes in MR before training, and the increase was significantly higher in boys, when intelligence was controlled. Without controlling intelligence, both sexes improved at the same rate. These results are consistent with two parallel studies that were carried out with preschool and secondary school students. The MR training did not produce any improvement in mathematical ability.

Keywords: Mental rotation, Spatial Training, Sex differences, Mathematics, Intelligence.

69 **1. Introduction**

70 Several studies carried out over the past 50 years state that spatial reasoning is key to
71 success in the so-called STEM disciplines –Sciences, Technology, Engineering and
72 Mathematics– (Shea, Lubinski, & Benbow, 2001; Wai, Lubinski, & Benbow, 2009).
73 Moreover, spatial reasoning is very important in different everyday tasks, such as driving,
74 following instructions to assemble a piece of furniture, or orientating in a given space.

75 In Uttal et al.'s (2013) meta-analysis, the magnitude, durability, and transfer of spatial
76 reasoning training were assessed through 206 studies. The results indicated that this type of
77 reasoning is malleable through training, both in men and women, and at different points in
78 the evolutionary cycle (children and adults). Most studies that have addressed this type of
79 training have been conducted on the adult population (as can be seen in Uttal et al.'s meta-
80 analysis, 2013), with those performed on children or adolescents being less frequent.

81 Spatial reasoning in children is essential; in fact, it is so closely linked to the
82 development of numerical comprehension that early spatial intelligence predicts a child's
83 performance in mathematics (Newcombe, Levine, & Mix, 2015; Verdine, Golinkoff, Hirsh-
84 Pasek, & Newcombe, 2017). For example, Zhang et al. (2014) have noted that young children
85 who are better at spatial visualization (i.e., detecting multiple spatial forms or shapes, rotating
86 or manipulating them in the imagination, and matching them to form a complete shape)
87 develop stronger arithmetic skills in Primary school. In some way, this could also be
88 determinant for the child's performance in later stages, in the sense that middle school
89 students (eighth-grade students; 13–15 years old) with better mental rotation (MR) abilities
90 are more likely to succeed in science (Ganley, Vasilyeva, & Dulaney, 2014).

91 Mental Rotation (hereinafter, MR), one of the spatial skills that has received most
92 attention from a psychometric and cognitive point of view, implies being able to mentally

93 manipulate bidimensional and tridimensional stimuli swiftly and accurately (Linn & Petersen,
94 1985).

95 The relationship that this ability has with academic performance, for example, in tasks
96 involving the representation of different perspectives in technical drawing, the resolution of
97 geometry problems or the understanding of molecular structures, leads this ability to acquire
98 a great interest within the STEM disciplines.

99

100 **1.1. Effects of Mental Rotation training**

101 Training with tasks that involve the rotation of stimuli and objects has been approached
102 in different studies, especially among the adult population (Adams, Stull, & Hegarty, 2014;
103 Larson et al., 1999; Meneghetti, Borella, & Pazzaglia, 2016; Wiedenbauer, Schmid, &
104 Jansen-Osmann, 2007; Wright, Thompson, Ganis, Newcombe, & Kosslyn, 2008) and on
105 earlier stages of development, such as puberty and adolescence (Bergner & Neubauer, 2011;
106 Neubauer, Bergner, & Schatz, 2010; Rodán, Contreras, Elosúa, & Gimeno, 2016; Sanz de
107 Acedo Lizarraga & García Ganuza, 2003). This type of MR training has been studied less
108 frequently in infancy and childhood, hence sometimes no learning effect of the ability to
109 rotate has been observed, as was the case in a study with 4-year-old children who did not
110 benefit from MR training (Frick, Ferrara, & Newcombe, 2013). There have also been very
111 few studies that have addressed the effect of training related to this spatial ability in the stage
112 of development close to adolescence and during childhood. The inclusion of a control group
113 (CG) has not always been considered at these stages of development (Brosnan, 1998; Chien,
114 1986; Clements, Battista, Sarama, & Swaminathan, 1997), which is determinant to study the
115 actual effectiveness of these interventions, as Uttal et al. (2013) suggested in their meta-
116 analysis. Other studies involving these age groups did not incorporate specific training, but

117 rather only included a test-retest assessment (Kaplan & Weisberg, 1987) or did not include
118 specific MR tasks, just training with tasks related to the representation of perspectives of
119 objects in 2-D parting from manipulative models in 3-D (Tillotson, 1984), with the graphic
120 design of 2-D and 3-D panoramas –objects in a landscape and navigational control–
121 (Shavaliar, 2004) or with stimuli perception as a whole from different angles (Tzuriel &
122 Egozi, 2010). To our knowledge, few studies have used specific MR material with children in
123 middle childhood (i.e., between 6-7 and puberty). De Lisi and Wolford (2002) used the well-
124 known video game "Tetris" to train this spatial ability in children aged 8 and 9 years, and
125 found an improvement and transfer effect towards a task different to the trained task – Card
126 Rotation Test. Cheng and Mix (2014) used a single 40-minute session to train children aged
127 between 6 and 8 years with a mental rotation task consisting of observing two parts of a flat
128 shape and then pointing out of the four pictures the one that shows the shape as a whole.
129 These authors only observed an improvement when the evaluated task was the same as the
130 trained one, but there was no transfer effect to another MR task (PMA-SR). On the other
131 hand, Hawes, Moss, Caswell, and Poliszczuk (2015) in a six-week training session (three
132 times a week, 15-20 minutes per session, 4.5 hours total) with children aged between 6 and 8
133 years, used up to three different types of computer games based on two-dimensional tasks
134 during MR training, none of which were the same as the assessment tasks. However, the
135 trained MR tasks did not produce a transfer to all the evaluated MR tasks, finding differences
136 in the improvement of both groups only in two of the four tasks evaluated, which the authors
137 defined as a near transfer. Another recent study carried out by this research group (Hawes,
138 Moss, Caswell, Naqvi, & MacKinnon, 2017) with children aged between 4 and 7 years,
139 performed a training based on geometrical concepts using a wide variety of in-class spatial
140 activities and lessons, of which several were related to MR (e.g., discovering 2D congruence

141 through rotations, discovering 3D equivalence through mental rotations of 3D cube
142 structures), using different tasks for training and assessment. Finally, in a recent study by
143 Lowrie, Logan, and Ramful (2017) with participants aged between 10 and 12 years, a spatial
144 10-week reasoning program which incorporated activities related to MR (e.g., 2D rotation
145 around a point), as well as visualization –Vz– and spatial orientation –SO activities, was
146 carried out. However, it is unknown whether the configuration of the items in the MR
147 training could be similar to those items that evaluate this same construct in the tests used by
148 these authors (SRI, Spatial Reasoning Instrument). Nevertheless, only Hawes et al.'s (2017)
149 and Lowrie et al.'s (2017) studies report finding transfer of the trained MR task towards
150 others that assess this same spatial ability. Therefore, taking into consideration all these
151 results, overall it seems that MR training does not always lead to a general improvement in
152 this spatial ability.

153

154 **1.2. Sex differences in MR**

155 Regarding the sex differences in this ability, different studies have shown that the
156 magnitude of the effect in MR seems to vary, with males being generally favored in terms of
157 performance in this spatial ability (e.g., Linn & Petersen, 1985; Maeda & Yoon, 2013; Voyer,
158 Voyer, & Bryden, 1995).

159 In relation to the study of the level of improvement of this spatial ability in both sexes
160 after an intervention, Marulis, Liu, Warren, Uttal, and Newcombe's (2007) meta-analysis
161 showed results that indicated a similar enhancement in the execution of both sexes when this
162 spatial ability was trained. It has also been observed that the males benefit more than females
163 after a spatial abilities training program related to Vz or MR (Patkin & Dayan, 2013; Rafi,
164 Samsudin, & Said, 2008).

165 **1.3. MR training and mathematics**

166 The relationship between spatial ability and mathematics has been demonstrated in
167 research where individuals with a better spatial performance often also perform better in
168 mathematics (e.g., Baenninger & Newcombe, 1995; Delgado & Prieto, 2004; Holmes,
169 Adams, & Hamilton, 2008; Rasmussen & Bisanz, 2005). In fact, a strong relationship
170 between MR spatial ability and mathematical performance has been observed among
171 kindergarten, 1st, 2nd and 3rd grade of Primary Education (Carr, Alexeev, Horan, Barsed, &
172 Wang, 2015; Cheng & Mix, 2014; Frick, 2018; Gunderson, Ramirez, Beilock, & Levine,
173 2012; Hawes et al., 2015; Mix et al., 2016; Thompson, Nuerk, Moeller, & Kadosh, 2013).
174 Such is the importance of the relationship between these two skills that it has also been
175 subject of study in order to analyze to what extent the practice of MR-related tasks can lead
176 to an improvement in the performance of certain mathematical tasks (Cheng & Mix, 2014;
177 Hawes et al., 2015; Hawes et al., 2017; Lowrie et al., 2017; Rodán et al., 2016).

178 The transfer effect that the practice of visuospatial tasks can have on mathematical
179 performance has been explored throughout the adolescent stage through some studies that
180 have used specific tasks or related to MR. Olkun, Altun and Smith (2005) found with Turkish
181 fourth and fifth -grade students a positive effect on the learning of geometry through a
182 computerized intervention with Tangram puzzles, a task involving rotation and combination
183 of pieces to form a pattern.

184 Some meta-analysis studies have shown small sex differences in favor of males in
185 mathematics (Reilly, Neumann, & Andrews, 2015). These gender differences can disappear
186 when controlling spatial ability (Wei, Chen, & Zhou, 2016), which shows that the
187 mathematical performance in favor of the male sex can be explained by gender differences in
188 spatial ability.

189 A less frequent issue in the literature is the study of the predisposition of students in
190 this stage of development towards their incorporation to science and mathematics courses
191 after a spatial intervention. For example, Sorby (2009) showed with middle school students -
192 generally 12-13 years old- that these students not only benefited from exercises centered on
193 3D drawing and spatial skills (mental rotation, scaling, and cross-sectioning), but also that
194 girls who underwent the spatial skills training went on to enroll in more follow-on math and
195 science courses than girls in a similarly identified comparison group. This author has
196 suggested that the optimal age for girls to participate in spatial skills training is likely in or
197 around middle school, and that high school interventions may be too late for most girls who
198 have established their poor self-efficacy beliefs about mathematics and science.

199 In earlier developmental stages, such as infancy and childhood, different and
200 inconclusive results have also been found, as it seems that the training of spatial abilities
201 (including MR) is transferred onto some mathematical tasks, but not to others. Cheng and
202 Mix (2014) found with children aged between 6 and 8 years that a single, 40-minute session
203 of MR training could improve performance in solving sums and subtractions –missing-term
204 equations–, but not in solving number fact problems, or in "multidigit calculation". The
205 authors of the study argued that the improvements in these tasks could be due to the fact that
206 MR shares cognitive processes similar to those that arise in solving simple equation problems
207 (e.g., $4 + _ = 11$ becomes $11 - 4 = _$). However, in Hawes et al.'s (2015) study with
208 children within the same age range –6 to 8 years–, it was observed that a computerized
209 training with up to 3 MR tasks did not transfer an improvement to nonverbal arithmetic task
210 and missing term problems, despite having a longer training period –4.5 hours in total over a
211 6-week period– than that in Cheng and Mix's (2014) study. Later, Hawes et al.'s (2017) study
212 with children aged between 4 and 7 years, assessed the effectiveness of a year-long

213 intervention. The study focused on spatial visualization skills related to geometry (MR tasks,
214 among others) and on determining the extent to which supporting children’s spatial thinking
215 skills might generalize to improvements in numerical performance. After the 32 weeks of
216 training in spatial reasoning, Hawes et al. observed a transfer only towards a symbolic
217 magnitude comparison tasks that involved comparing pairs of Arabic numerals (digits), but
218 not towards other mathematical tasks of advanced number knowledge and calculations skills.
219 These authors posed that it was the combination of spatial curricula that brought about
220 significant change but suggested that “tightly controlled research studies are needed to test
221 the activities and lessons in isolation or in various combinations to determine their relative
222 effectiveness” (Hawes et al., 2017, p. 24). In this sense, it would be interesting to assess how
223 an intensive training of a single spatial construct, such as MR, could have an effect on
224 mathematical performance.

225 In relation to Lowrie et al.’s (2017) visuospatial reasoning (VSR) intervention with
226 children aged between 10 and 12 years, an improvement in mathematical performance
227 (geometry-measurement concepts and number concepts) was observed. These authors
228 suggested that future work on the impact of visuospatial training on mathematical
229 performance includes a broader participant base, especially including more grades across
230 elementary schools. On the other hand, Mix et al. (2016) have called for future research using
231 training to contrast this relationship between spatial ability and mathematics and have pointed
232 out that “only training experiments can determine whether these latent abilities are malleable
233 and whether this training generalizes to academic learning” (Mix et al., 2016, p. 1222).

234 In view of the varied results found to date in the few studies that have focused on these
235 spatial skills, and the methodological differences between them, we believe that further

236 research is needed to better understand the impact of MR training on mathematical ability at
237 this stage of development.

238

239 **1.4. Rationale and aim of the present study**

240 Based on previous research on spatial skills among children, it would be interesting to
241 study the degree of improvement in both sexes through a computerized MR intervention
242 program on this type of population, in addition to assessing the link between mental rotation
243 skills and mathematics, at this age of development. As Newcombe and Frick have pointed
244 out, it is important “to promote spatial thinking in preschools, at home, and in children’s play,
245 integrating spatial content into formal and informal instruction could not only improve spatial
246 functioning in general but also reduce differences related to gender and socioeconomic status
247 that may impede full participation in a technological society” (Newcombe & Frick, 2010, p.
248 102). Promoting spatial reasoning throughout primary education levels could be a key factor
249 for children to arrive at an optimal level of visuospatial reasoning to later stages, such as
250 adolescence, in which scholars must determine which path they wish to follow (Humanities,
251 Sciences/Technology, or Art) that will become crucial in their upcoming professional career.
252 Therefore, any kind of spatial intervention that takes place before adolescence could be
253 crucial, especially when the presence of women is scarce in certain degrees where
254 mathematics and science –and therefore spatial reasoning– are important. This study
255 evaluates the effects of MR training on primary school children (6-8 years) on the spatial and
256 mathematical performance. Thus, MR training programs taking place prior to adolescence
257 could be crucial, in particular, in areas where women are scarce, such as in certain degrees
258 where mathematics and science –and therefore spatial thinking– are important. The present
259 study will provide further evidence towards the different varied results obtained in previous

260 studies that have assessed the effects of MR training on primary school children on their
261 spatial and mathematical performance, and the possible sex differences in relation to this
262 mental rotation skill are considered.

263

264 **1.5. Goals and hypothesis**

265 Focusing on the present study, our first objective was to examine improvements in
266 visuospatial abilities after conducting a MR training program. Taking into consideration that
267 spatial abilities are malleable and that it is possible that they could improve after the
268 completion of a training program, we hypothesized that the improvement in the experimental
269 group (EG) on the assessed spatial task would be significantly more pronounced than in the
270 control group (CG). The second objective was to evaluate the average sex differences in
271 spatial ability before and after training. In both phases, we hypothesized that the spatial
272 performance would be greater in boys, who would benefit more than girls from the training
273 program (Patkin & Dayan, 2013; Rafi et al., 2008). Given the overlap between general
274 intelligence and spatial abilities (e.g., Lohman, 1996), and that there are no sex differences in
275 intelligence (Halpern & Lamay, 2000, Neisser et al., 1996), it seems appropriate to measure
276 intelligence for control purposes, assessing whether sex differences in spatial ability in favor
277 of the group of males are diluted when intelligence intervenes. Finally, the third objective
278 was to analyze the effect of MR training on math ability, as well as the relationship between
279 both abilities. Taking into account previous studies yielding evidences towards significant
280 changes, our hypothesis was that there could be a significant effect of spatial training
281 improving mathematical competence. On the other hand, and due to the relationship between
282 spatial skills and mathematics, we expect that boys will have a better performance in the
283 mathematical task (Reilly et al., 2015), finding a time x group x sex interaction.

284 2. Method

285 2.1. Participants

286 In this study, a total of 92 students of 2nd year Primary education from two Public
287 schools in Madrid, Spain, located in a downtown area, with a medium-high sociocultural
288 level, took part and completed experimental sessions. Finally, 11 participants from the CG
289 and the EG were not included in the analyses because they had missed some parts of the
290 study (i.e., pretest and/or posttest). There were two EG participants who, having completed
291 the pre and posttest phases, missed one of the training sessions, but despite this, these
292 participants were finally included in the final analyses. Thus, the final sample consisted of 81
293 participants ($M = 7.69$ years of age, $SD = 0.62$). In the EG, there was a total of 42 students
294 ($M = 7.69$ years of age, $SD = 0.66$; 18 boys-24 girls) and in the CG, there were 39 students
295 ($M = 7.70$ years of age, $SD = 0.55$; 19 boys-20 girls). Both schools had two classes for 2nd
296 grade. The classes were randomly assigned to the CG and the EG.

297

298 2.2. Materials

299 2.2.1. *Raven's Progressive Matrices (Standard Progressives Matrices; Raven, Court, &*
300 *Raven, 1996)*. This task assesses the intelligence or g factor. The reliability of the test
301 indicates a rate of two halves of up to 0.90, while the test-retest varies between 0.83 and 0.90
302 (Seisdedos, 1995). It can be applied from 6 years of age until adulthood. It consists of 60
303 problems divided into 5 series (ABCDE) with 12 elements each, with no time limit, with an
304 estimated 40-90 minutes duration. Each correct answer is assigned a point, so that the
305 maximum test score is 60 points. The application of the test was performed as described in
306 the manual.

307 2.2.2. *Spatial ability test "E" from EFAI-1*. It corresponds to a spatial subtest within the
308 battery of tests of the *Factorial Assessment of Intellectual Skills* (Santamaría, Arribas, Pereña,
309 & Seisdedos, 2005). This task assesses the ability and agility to mentally imagine an object's
310 movements and transformations in space (p. 17). The EFAI authors have found reliability
311 coefficients of 0.86 for the First Level of this task (Santamaría et al., 2005). The test is
312 appropriate for students between 7 and 10 years of age and consists of 30 evaluation
313 exercises plus two practice examples, with four responses for each item. The task requires the
314 subject to imagine mental movements and transformations, as only one of the four stimuli on
315 the right side fits into the white space on the left of the puzzle, which is usually composed of
316 one, two or more parts (Figure 1). The duration of the test is six minutes. Each correct answer
317 is assigned a point, so that the maximum test score is 30 points. The application of the test
318 was carried out as described in the manual.

319 2.2.3. *Numerical aptitude test "N" from EFAI-1*. From the same test battery of the EFAI-1,
320 this task assesses the participant's ability to manipulate numerical symbols and to reason
321 procedurally with information and quantitative relationships. The authors have found
322 reliability coefficients of 0.94 for the First Level of this task (Santamaría et al., 2005). The
323 test is appropriate for students between 7 and 10 years of age and involves four examples and
324 30 evaluation exercises, each of them with four possible responses but with only one correct
325 answer. The exercises require three different categories of tasks: 1) seven items
326 corresponding to operations that decide which will yield a greater or smaller result,
327 depending on the case, assessing the ability to handle numerical symbols and to quickly and
328 skillfully perform basic math operations (arithmetic); 2) 15 items corresponding to word
329 problems, where the subject is required to decipher which is the key information needed,
330 reformulating the problem in terms of numbers (which problem/operation or problems should

331 be performed) and to make any calculations to find the right solution; and 3) eight items
332 corresponding to two problems with numerical information in chart or table format,
333 interpreting, locating and calculating the information needed to find the correct solution to a
334 series of questions using the information presented (4 questions for each of the two
335 problems). The duration of the test is 14 minutes. Each correct answer is assigned a point, so
336 that the maximum test score is 30 points. The application of the test was carried out as
337 described in the manual.

338 *2.2.4. Mental Rotation Training Program (MRTP).* To adjust the mental rotation test to the
339 age of the study's participants, three pilot studies were carried out. In the first two studies, 10
340 children from 2nd year of Primary Education from Public Schools took part. They were
341 carried out on paper and help was requested in order to make decisions about the type of task
342 to use. Afterwards, a third pilot study was conducted on six children from 2nd year of
343 Primary, applying the final computer program to assess fatigue, difficulty, approximate time
344 and student motivation.

345 To design the stimuli of the computerized training program for mental rotation in two
346 dimensions, the computer software Corel Draw® Graphics Suite X3 (Corel Corporation,
347 2007) was used, using its nomenclature regarding the degrees of rotation. The program
348 consists of 450 slides. Each slide consists of: 1) a white figure or mold (target), placed on the
349 left side of the presentation, and 2) a pair of stimuli placed on the right side, numbered as "1"
350 and "2", and identical to the mold, but with different orientations with respect to such mold.
351 These stimuli are bidimensional and the orientation of the rotated stimuli is 90°, 180° and
352 270°. The flipped stimulus (which does not fit the mold) can be a mirror image of the mold
353 across the X or Y axis or across the X axis with an additional rotation of 90° or 270°. In
354 Session1, stimuli are only rotated 90° or 270°. In Sessions 2 and 3, rotations are of 90°, 270°

355 or 180°. Finally, the difficulty of the task is also manipulated according to the characteristics
356 of the stimuli, which change from close and concrete figures (Figure 2A) to abstract figures
357 (Figures 2B and 2C), increasing the complexity of the figures within the same session and
358 between sessions. The attributes relative to the orientation of the rotated stimuli (angular
359 disparity) are counterbalanced across different phases and sessions of the MRTP. The MRTP
360 task requires that the participant imagines the movements corresponding to transformations
361 and MR, deciding which of the two stimuli “1” or “2” match the mold only if it is turned or
362 rotated, taking into account that only one will fit (see Figures 2 and 3).

363 In order to program, present the stimuli and collect the data from MRTP, the E-prime
364 version 1.0 software (Psychology Software Tools, 2002) was used.

365

366 **2.3. Procedure**

367 All tests were administered in six days, spread over two consecutive weeks, and divided
368 into the following three phases:

369 *2.3.1. Pretest.* The test took place in the students’ usual classroom. The approximate duration
370 was 120 minutes. Participants were observed by two experimenters. The following tests were
371 administered collectively, in the following order, leaving a resting time of five minutes
372 between each test: Raven's Progressive Matrices SPM version, "E" spatial ability tests and
373 "N" numerical ability test from the EFAI-1.

374 *2.3.2. Training.* This phase was carried out in the school’s computer room on the
375 experimental group. It was composed of three sessions, each with a duration of
376 approximately 30 minutes, and with a total duration of 90 minutes for the training, although
377 duration could vary according to each participant as there was no time constraint for the
378 responses in each of the sheets. The training session had two phases. The practice phase

379 consisted of 10 trials aimed at familiarizing the students with the task and ensuring they
380 understand the task. One of the characteristics of this phase is that every slide shows an
381 animation where the progressive rotation of each stimulus is observed to see if the shape fits
382 or not into the target, thereby facilitating the understanding of the task (Figure 3). Similar to
383 the rest of the training program, each slide presented feedback, confirming whether or not
384 they had answered correctly. Within each trial, and just before the presentation of the rotated
385 stimuli, a fixation stimulus of 250 ms was shown. Additionally, between the presentation of
386 the feedback stimulus and the fixation stimulus of the consecutive trial, there was an
387 Interstimulus Interval (ISI) of 500 ms. (Figure 4). Before each training session, the
388 researchers highlighted to the children the importance that precision and quality –rather than
389 response time– would have for the task and insisted that they should take as much time as
390 they needed to ensure a correct response. The training phase, consisting of 150 slides divided
391 into two blocks of 75 slides each with a 5-minute break between them. The number of hits
392 and the response time for each participant in each of the sessions were recorded, although the
393 specific analysis of the individual differences in training was not an objective of the present
394 study.

395 While the experimental group performed the training phase, the control group
396 performed their normal class, which never coincided with any mathematics class.

397 *2.3.3. Posttest.* The following tests were administered according to the timetables established
398 by the school: Raven SPM version, and "E" and "N" subtests from the EFAI-1.

399

400 **2.4. Data Analyses**

401 Statistical analyses were performed in SPSS, version 24.0 (IBM Corp. Released 2016)
402 with a significance level of 0.05. To confirm that both groups, and both sexes were

403 comparable in the cognitive abilities evaluated, a three-way ANOVA was performed for the
404 three dependent variables (Raven, EFAI-E and EFAI-N). A subsequent mixed-design 2×2×2
405 ANOVA with group (experimental, control) and sex (boys, girls) as the between-subjects
406 factors and time (pretest, posttest) as the within-subjects factor, and using the initial scores of
407 intelligence (Raven pretest) as covariate, was applied to the two dependent variables EFAI-E
408 and EFAI-N. Thus, it would be possible to assess possible improvements in spatial and
409 mathematical skills, by evaluating the main effects and possible interactions, while
410 controlling for intelligence.

411 3. Results

412 3.1. Preliminary Analyses in Pretest

413 The preliminary analysis showed that both groups did not differ in the scores of the
414 different tasks evaluated in the pretest phase in any of the tasks: **Raven:** $F(1, 77) = .19$, MSE
415 $= 19.3$, $p = .66$, $\eta_p^2 = .002$; **EFAI-E:** $F(1, 77) = .18$, $MSE = 2.88$, $p \geq .67$, $\eta_p^2 = .002$; **EFAI-**
416 **N:** $F(1, 77) = .36$, $MSE = 18.2$, $p \geq .55$, $\eta_p^2 = .005$. The results also revealed no sex
417 differences neither for the entire sample [**Raven:** $F(1, 77) = 1.15$, $MSE = 116.8$, $p = .29$, η_p^2
418 $= .015$; **EFAI-E:** $F(1, 77) = 1.32$, $MSE = 21.4$, $p = .25$, $\eta_p^2 = .017$; **EFAI-N:** $F(1, 77) = .56$,
419 $MSE = 28.4$, $p = .46$, $\eta_p^2 = .007$], nor by intervention group [**Raven:** $F(1, 77) = .20$, $MSE =$
420 20.0 , $p = .66$, $\eta_p^2 = .003$; **EFAI-E:** $F(1, 77) = .90$, $MSE = 14.6$, $p = .35$, $\eta_p^2 = .012$; **EFAI-N:**
421 $F(1, 77) = .08$, $MSE = 4.16$, $p = .78$, $\eta_p^2 = .001$]. The descriptive statistics of the different
422 variables evaluated in EG and CG are shown in Table 1. The descriptive statistics of the
423 different variables evaluated in boys and girls are shown in Table 2 and 3, for the CG and the
424 EG respectively.

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427 **Table 1.** Means and standard deviations for measures for the two phases in both groups.

Measure	Total (N = 81)			
	CG (n = 39)		EG (n = 42)	
	M	SD	M	SD
Raven (max.=60)				
Pretest	29.41	9.47	30.62	10.55
Posttest	30.54	10.65	34.05	11.24
Increase	1.13	4.64	3.43	4.32
EFAI-E (max.=30)				
Pretest	9.82	4.12	9.45	3.95
Posttest	13.62	5.32	16.21	5.51
Increase	3.79	4.56	6.76	5.03
EFAI-N (max.=30)				
Pretest	13.1	6.87	14.02	7.21
Posttest	15.9	3.71	16.00	7.13
Increase	2.77	3.12	1.98	3.44

* Pairwise comparisons (Mean difference).

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438 **Table 2.** Means and standard deviations for measures for the two phases and both sexes in the
 439 CG.

Measure	Control Group (N = 39)			
	Boys (n = 19)		Girls (n = 20)	
	M	SD	M	SD
Raven (max.=60)				
Pretest	28.68	8.75	30.10	10.29
Posttest	30.53	10.80	30.55	10.78
Increase	1.84	4.65	0.45	4.64
EFAI-E (max.=30)				
Pretest	10.79	4.86	8.90	3.11
Posttest	15.16	6.23	12.15	3.91
Increase	4.37	5.35	3.25	3.73
EFAI-N (max.=30)				
Pretest	13.95	6.93	12.30	6.89
Posttest	16.68	6.86	15.10	6.66
Increase	2.74	3.09	2.80	3.24

* Pairwise comparisons (Mean difference)

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450 **Table 3.** Means and standard deviations for measures for the two phases and both sexes in the
 451 EG.

Measure	Experimental Group (N = 42)			
	Boys (n = 18)		Girls (n = 24)	
	M	SD	M	SD
Raven (max.=60)				
Pretest	28.67	11.23	32.08	10.0
Posttest	31.89	12.25	35.67	10.39
Increase	3.22	4.05	3.58	4.60
EFAI-E (max.=30)				
Pretest	9.56	4.57	9.38	3.51
Posttest	17.94	5.73	14.92	5.06
Increase	8.39	5.35	5.54	4.51
EFAI-N (max.=30)				
Pretest	14.44	7.93	13.71	6.78
Posttest	16.44	7.69	15.67	6.82
Increase	2.00	3.60	1.96	3.39

* Pairwise comparisons (Mean difference)

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454 3.2. Effects of training and sex differences

455 Introducing intelligence (Raven pretest) as covariate, the 2×2×2 ANOVA did not show
 456 on the spatial task (EFAI-E) a significant main effect due to time, $F(1, 77) = .077$, $MSE =$
 457 $.723$, $p = .78$, $\eta_p^2 = .001$, nor an interaction time x sex x group, $F(1, 77) = 1.19$, $MSE =$
 458 11.20 , $p = .28$, $\eta_p^2 = .015$. However, significant interactions between the “time” factor and
 459 the covariate [$F(1, 77) = 15.70$, $MSE = 148.27$, $p < .001$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.17$], time × group [$F(1, 77)$
 460 $= 9.30$, $MSE = 87.75$, $p = .003$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.11$] and between time x sex [$F(1, 77) = 6.28$, $MSE =$
 461 59.33 , $p = .014$, $\eta_p^2 = 0.8$] were found. Pairwise comparisons applying the Bonferroni

462 correction showed that the interaction between time x group was explained as the increase in
463 EFAI-E score being significantly greater in the EG than in the CG ($\Delta = 6.90$ vs. $\Delta = 3.94$; p
464 $= .003$). Comparisons with Bonferroni also showed that the increase in EFAI-E score was
465 greater in boys than in girls ($\Delta = 6.64$ vs. $\Delta = 4.19$; $p = .014$). It is worth noting that when
466 intelligence was not controlled for in the ANOVA (i.e., without using Raven as a covariate),
467 the sex x time interaction was not significant for spatial ability [$F(1, 77) = 3.50$, $MSE =$
468 39.35 , $p = .065$, $\eta_p^2 = .04$, Bonferroni's post-hoc, **EFAI-E**: $\Delta = 6.38$ vs. $\Delta = 4.40$; $p = .065$].
469 This aspect will be further discussed in the "Discussion" section.

470 The other ANOVA analysis for the mathematical task (EFAI-N) only showed a
471 significant main effect due to time, $F(1, 77) = 3.89$, $MSE = 21.92$, $p = .05$, $\eta_p^2 = .05$. A post-
472 hoc analysis used to assess mathematical ability by category (arithmetic, word problems and
473 problems created after extracting information from a table context) showed only an effect of
474 time for the variable EFAI-N (Tables): $F(1, 77) = 6.14$, $MSE = 12.53$, $p = .015$, $\eta_p^2 = .08$].
475 No significant interactions were found either for time x sex [$F(1, 77) = .000$, $MSE = .001$, p
476 $= .99$, $\eta_p^2 = .00$], or for time x group [$F(1, 77) = 1.11$, $MSE = 6.23$, $p = .30$, $\eta_p^2 = .01$], nor
477 for time x group x sex [$F(1, 77) = .005$, $MSE = .03$, $p = .94$, $\eta_p^2 = .00$].

478 Figure 5 shows the time x group x sex interactions of the two measures EFAI-E (panel
479 A) and EFAI-N (panel B).

480

481 **4. Discussion**

482 In this section, the relevant results found are discussed, in relation to the previous
483 literature, for each hypothesis of the study.

484 **4.1. Improvement effects on Mental Rotation**

485 The main objective of our study was to assess whether a MR training program (MRTP)
486 could improve visuospatial abilities in boys and girls in 2nd year of Primary school. To that
487 end, a MRTP in two dimensions was designed and applied to an experimental group,
488 comparing the EFAI-E scores between the pretest and posttest with respect to a control
489 group. The results of the study showed significant differences in the score for the EFAI-E
490 between experimental and control groups. Although both groups improved by the learning
491 effect in the application of the test in the pre and posttest phase, the experimental group's
492 improvement was significantly higher compared to the control group. This result is very
493 positive since previous studies have shown that favoring spatial reasoning is not only key in
494 enhancing success in STEM disciplines, but also appears to help strengthen skills that
495 promote children's integral development at this age (e.g., Newcombe & Frick, 2010).

496 There are several noteworthy aspects in our training program. In our study, the items
497 and the training program (MRTP) were different from those used to evaluate the spatial
498 ability test "E" EFAI-1 (Santamaría et al., 2005), an important aspect to consider when
499 assessing whether a transfer of the trained ability, in this case MR, exists. In previous studies
500 focused on individuals with similar age range as that of our present study, the same task has
501 been used for both training and assessment, although using different items (Cheng & Mix,
502 2014; Erlich et al., 2006; Kail & Park, 1990; Wiedenbauer & Jansen-Osmann, 2008).
503 However, this approach may not allow to completely assess the transfer of a trained ability.
504 In our study, both the evaluation and the training tasks imply that the participant mentally
505 imagines movements and transformations (i.e., rotations) of an object in a two-dimensional
506 plane. Although the format of both tasks is different, as can be seen in the "*Materials*"
507 section, both could be similar in terms of the type of cognitive demand, thus, it is reasonable
508 to categorize it as near transfer, similarly to Hawes et al. (2015).

509 Another relevant aspect of the present study is that it included a CG, which is essential
510 in order to have a real understanding of the effectiveness of this type of interventions and
511 which is lacking in many previous studies, as Uttal et al. (2013) pointed out in their meta-
512 analysis. To date, not many studies have incorporated a CG using a specific MR training (De
513 Lisi & Wolford, 2002; Cheng & Mix, 2014; Hawes, et al., 2015; 2017; Lowrie et al., 2017).
514 All these studies, with the exception of De Lisi & Wolford's study, have tried to additionally
515 assess the degree of implication that the MR training has over the possible improvement in
516 mathematical performance. Therefore, later we will discuss the implication of the results
517 obtained towards this academic ability in relation to these studies. Some differences that
518 could be highlighted between the present study and those that have used specific MR training
519 materials, which not always include an analysis of sex differences or the relationship with
520 other variables of interest such as experience with video games or spatial anxiety. Next, the
521 hypotheses of our study will be discussed in relation to those variables not analyzed in
522 previous MR training studies among this age group.

523

524 **4.2. Spatial performance between sexes**

525 The second objective of our study was to evaluate the average sex differences in spatial
526 ability, and the influence of training on both sexes. In our study, no differences were found
527 between sex groups in the initial assessment, in line with other studies that found no sex
528 effect for some of the conditions evaluated (e.g., Hawes et al., 2017; Lowrie et al., 2017;
529 Neubauer et al., 2010; Rodán et al., 2016). In terms of sex differences in spatial ability after
530 training, our results showed an interaction of time x sex, so that a greater general
531 improvement was seen in boys rather than in girls in the MR spatial ability. However, there
532 was no significant interaction of time x sex x group, and these results are in accordance with

533 those of other studies on similar age groups who obtained similar improvements in spatial
534 performance for both sexes, or a training effect that equates the means in performance of both
535 sexes with tasks related to MR (Clements et al., 1997; Tzuriel & Egozi, 2010) or specific to
536 MR (De Lisi & Wolford, 2002; Ehrlich, Levine, & Goldin-Meadow, 2006). However, it is
537 worth noting that when intelligence was not controlled for in the analyses, the sex x time
538 interaction was not significant for spatial ability. Therefore, this result seems to indicate that
539 girls could be "compensating" spatial ability with general intelligence, so that by controlling
540 or leaving out of the analysis that variable, the differences between boys and girls appear in
541 the performance of the spatial ability. In fact, although in our study we did not find
542 significant sex differences in intelligence, a result that is in line with the findings found in the
543 reviewed literature on intelligence studies (Halpern & Lamay, 2000, Neisser et al., 1996), the
544 scores obtained by the girls in the Raven were higher in both groups, and before and after the
545 intervention, although these average differences between sex groups did not reach statistical
546 significance. This finding could explain, therefore, that the somewhat lesser spatial ability on
547 average of girls could be compensated and would be equated to the spatial performance of
548 boys thanks to general intelligence.

549 The present research obtained results which are convergent with those of previous
550 studies carried out on preschoolers and adolescents using a methodology parallel to that of
551 the present study, adapting the difficulty to the age group, yielding a similar improvement in
552 the MR performance of both sexes, and showing no differences between males and females
553 either before or after training on preschoolers (Fernández-Méndez, Contreras, & Elosúa,
554 2018a; Fernández-Méndez, Contreras, & Elosúa, 2018b) or on adolescents (Rodán et al.,
555 2016). These consistent results that replicate an experimental effect of training, of a trained
556 group versus a control group, across 3 different educational stages and using parallel

557 methodologies, represent an improvement on the limitation pointed out by Uttal et al. (2013).
558 These authors have noted the difficulty in finding comparable studies across different
559 development stages. Our studies show a similar pattern occurring across preschool, primary
560 and secondary education: the effect of a training program –which is similar in format and
561 duration– assessed through an improvement in a spatial task different to that used in training.
562 Moreover, no differences were found between sexes or between pre- and post-training in any
563 of the 3 development stages.

564

565 **4.3. Effects of MR training in mathematics**

566 The link between space and mathematics has been observed in several investigations,
567 including MR tasks related to spatial representation of numbers, i.e.: number line mapping
568 task and numerical comparison task in adults (Thompson et al., 2013), missing terms and
569 nonverbal arithmetic tasks (Hawes et al., 2015), and symbolic and non-symbolic comparison
570 and number knowledge tasks (Hawes et al., 2017) with children. In relation to these findings,
571 Mix et al. (2016) have confirmed that spatial ability and mathematics are separate but broadly
572 overlapping domains with a few skills that exhibit particularly strong cross-domain linkages,
573 and this happens at different ages from kindergarten to sixth grade. More recently, Frick
574 (2018) has shown, using a longitudinal approach that MR measured through different tasks in
575 first grade (7.5 years old; Card Rotation Test) and second grade (8.3 years old; Figure
576 Rotation) are positively correlated to mathematics and geometry performance in second
577 grade. Additionally, Frick's work reported that the MR -along with spatial scaling-, was a
578 strong predictor for Arithmetic Operations as well as for Numeric-Logical and Spatial
579 Functions (completing number sequences, counting magnitudes, counting cubes, estimating
580 line lengths) in children at the end of second grade.

581 In the present study, a significant effect of improvement in mathematical ability after
582 MR training was not found. This lack of transfer towards mathematics could be due to certain
583 methodological issues, such as the short duration (90 minutes in total) of our training
584 program. To date, only two studies working with this same age range (6 to 8 years) have
585 reported non-conclusive results when assessing the transfer of a MR training program
586 towards mathematical performance. Although the duration of this study has been shorter than
587 in previous studies, with the exception of Mix and Cheng's study, we doubt that the problem
588 of transfer towards mathematics is due to the design of the training or the duration of the
589 program. In our opinion, the program has been intense (150 trials per session) despite its
590 relatively short duration. It was highly motivating for the participants (in general, they
591 displayed a high level of enthusiasm, and even sometimes rivalry) and acted as positive
592 reinforcement due to the type of format of the program (such as the practice phase where they
593 could visualize the rotations progressively and obtain feedback regarding their success
594 throughout this phase). We do not know whether a program with a longer duration that
595 worked with the same MR spatial construct would have produced more changes in
596 mathematical performance. The MR training carried out by Hawes et al. (2015) with children
597 of the same age range did not produce improvements in a nonverbal exact arithmetic task, nor
598 in missing terms problems, even though the training program was longer than that of the
599 present study (4.5 hours). Similarly, Mix and Cheng (2014) in a single 40-minute training
600 session only found transfer towards a mathematical task of missing-term equations. The
601 results obtained in the other two reference studies that involve childhood are somewhat
602 different. Hawes et al.'s (2017) most recent intervention with children aged between 4 and 7
603 years only observed a transfer towards a basic numerical processing task –symbolic
604 magnitude comparison– but not towards other calculations skills after 32 weeks. To date, this

605 has been the longest study in terms of spatial reasoning intervention, using a wide variety of
606 activities that evaluate different skills including MR. On the other hand, Lowrie et al.'s
607 (2017) intervention lasted approximately 20 hours spread over 10 weeks, and found an
608 improvement in geometry and number concepts, after training children aged between 10 and
609 12 years in three different spatial constructs (MR, Vz and SO).

610 A tentative explanation to understand why there was no transfer from the spatial to the
611 mathematical, could be the influence of other factors, which could be important to learning of
612 mathematics. For example, some authors have linked linguistic skills –i.e., vocabulary, verbal
613 reasoning, etc.– with mathematical skills in the early school years (e.g., LeFevre et al., 2010),
614 and it has been reported that language at age 7 is a stronger predictor of mathematics in
615 comparison to spatial skills (Gilligan, Flouri & Farran, 2017). If linguistic skills have more
616 weight than spatial skills in this stage of the development (childhood), our group of students
617 may have also needed to resort more to the linguistic cognitive domain (more than to the
618 spatial one) to perform the mathematical exercises, especially those problems with a text in
619 the form of a statement (in total, 15 of 30 items in the measurement test), that is, word
620 problems where the subject is required to decipher which is the key information needed,
621 reformulating the problem in terms of numbers and to make any calculations to find the right
622 solution.

623 An alternative explanation is that a gradual shifting relationship between spatial skill
624 and mathematics from kindergarten to sixth grade could be due to changes in the demands of
625 mathematics content, developmental changes in spatial skill, or both (Mix et al., 2016). The
626 regression analyzes performed by these authors have shown at an age very similar to ours
627 (third grade children; 7-9 years) several significant effects involving MR, however these
628 effects were less than those found for children in either kindergarten or sixth grade. This

629 could explain why, in our age group, the trained mental rotation did not transfer to the
630 mathematical tasks.

631 These aspects could be, at least in part, the reason why some interventions have a
632 greater transfer effect than others in mathematical performance, beyond the duration of the
633 intervention programs themselves. Lowrie et al.'s (2017) study is quite extensive, but shorter
634 in duration than that of Hawes et al. (2017) and does produce a transfer towards mathematical
635 performance. However, a post-hoc analysis (see text added at the bottom of page 179) carried
636 out to separate the mathematical tasks into number-based and geometry questions revealed
637 that the improvement occurred only for the items linked to geometry-measurement concepts,
638 but not to the number concepts. In the present study, the post-hoc analysis carried out to
639 analyze by mathematical categories (arithmetic, word problems and mathematical problems
640 from the information extracted from data organized in tables) has not shown any
641 improvement in any of them. It is important to note the strong workload of purely spatial
642 content that our program had, in this case focused on the MR construct, and without
643 addressing aspects or approaches related to mathematics. In relation to this, Hawes et al.
644 (2017) pointed out that "it remains possible that changes in student thinking were specific to
645 our approach to mathematics professional development and not necessarily to a consequence
646 of the targeted spatial instruction per say" (p.24).

647 The results obtained in terms of the absence of differences between sex groups in
648 mathematical ability are in line with the fact that these differences are minimal or non-
649 existent in this cognitive ability during the primary education stage (e.g., Lachance &
650 Mazzocco, 2006; Miller & Halpern, 2014).

651 Based on this series of considerations, the present study is an additional contribution in
652 the field of spatial reasoning interventions. The null effects in terms of the transfer towards

653 mathematics in our study should serve as a further reflection so that in future spatial
654 reasoning interventions, the most appropriate approaches and designs are used to provide
655 children with the intertwined nature and unavoidable overlap between spatial and numerical
656 processing skills inherent to many intervention activities (Hawes et al., 2017).

657 Moreover, it is noteworthy that some meta-analyses have addressed sex differences in
658 spatial processing (e.g., Voyer et al., 1995) and in mathematics and science (Reilly,
659 Neumann, & Andrews, 2015), as well as the malleability of spatial abilities (Uttal et al.,
660 2013), but, to date, there are no meta-analyses or systematic reviews that study the effects of
661 improving spatial abilities and their transfer to mathematics. In this sense, we believe that the
662 results of our experimental study, together with the existing findings in the literature on
663 spatial ability interventions -more specifically, mental rotation- and their relation or transfer
664 towards mathematics at different ages, could be the way to obtain new conclusions in future
665 meta-analysis studies and thus, find what is the most operational way to perform this type of
666 training programs, perhaps with interventions focused on other types of spatial tasks that are
667 more involved in mathematics, or that are perform during longer periods, or both. The search
668 for new approaches to optimize this type of interventions could help minimize the risks of a
669 failed intervention that consumes considerable educational resources.

670

671 **4.4. Limitations of the Study and Future Research**

672 Next, certain limitations of the present study are discussed in order to take them into
673 account when performing future research on this topic. One of these limitations is the
674 relatively short duration of the training program, which could have repercussions on its
675 effects both on durability and the transfer of learning towards other activities of everyday life.
676 The transfer effects of spatial to mathematical ability do not occur suddenly/immediately.

677 Therefore, we urge that future longitudinal works, similar to Frick's (2018), should be carried
678 out, but within specific spatial skills (MR or others) training field, in order to study how the
679 transfer of the spatial to specific mathematical tasks occurs, and at different stages of
680 development, comparing the possible transfer between these cognitive domains among a
681 training group compared to another that does not perform spatial training. This could be in
682 line with Frick's (2018) suggestion, who pointed out that "Gaining a better understanding of
683 the specific subcomponents of spatial ability, as well as their early developments and
684 consequences for later success in mathematics, could be instrumental for developing
685 purposeful and well-directed interventions" (Frick, 2018, p. 2).

686 The influence of other factors not evaluated in the present study, such as linguistic
687 skills, could be a relevant aspect to better understand the variables that influence learning and
688 improvement of spatial abilities and their transfer to mathematical performance. Therefore, it
689 would be plausible to include tests that evaluate linguistic aspects in order to control their
690 influence on individual differences in mathematical performance, especially in verbal
691 problems. Another interesting example could be self-reported performance of pre and post
692 training. The results show that boys and girls have performed equally in our training program,
693 but have they perceived this themselves? What do they think about their effectiveness and
694 their spatial performance? This would be a stimulating route to explore in future studies, as
695 the influence of stereotypes on the modulation of sex differences has already been
696 demonstrated (i.e., Moé, 2012, 2016).

697 While it was not one of objectives of the present study, it is important to note as an
698 additional limitation that the small sample size could affect the conclusions about the absence
699 of sex differences in mathematical ability. However, it is also true that literature on this topic

700 has shown that sex differences in mathematical ability at this stage of development are
701 extremely small (Cohen's $d = .07$; see Reilly et al., 2015).

702 Finally, in future research, we will explore the specific analysis of the individual
703 differences in training applied according to the difficulty conditions of the items in relation to
704 the degrees of rotation or concrete vs. abstract stimuli. This objective has not been included
705 in the present study, which has focused on exploring the effect of training by comparing
706 experimental and control groups.

707

708 **5. Conclusions**

709 As far as the contributions of this study are concerned, this work is one of the first
710 researches at the childhood stage that analyzes several aspects. To date, only Cheng and
711 Mix's (2014) and Hawes et al.'s (2015) studies have evaluated with children aged between 6
712 and 8 years the influence that a MR training program can have on the mathematical field, but
713 such previous studies have not considered other factors, such as sex differences. In the
714 present study, we have evaluated the degree of improvement provided by a computer
715 program with MR tasks, including a CG—a key aspect that has not always been considered in
716 spatial training—and the possible relationship between MR and mathematical competence in
717 boys and girls aged between 7 and 8 years. Our results showed a significant improvement in
718 MR of the experimental group in relation to the control. There were no differences between
719 sexes in MR before training, and the increase was significantly higher in boys when
720 intelligence was controlled, and without controlling intelligence both sexes improved at the
721 same rate in MR. The MR training did not produce any improvement in mathematical ability.

722

723

724 **Notes**

725 Similar to other authors (e.g., Hawes et al., 2017), the present study uses the terms "spatial
726 thinking", "spatial reasoning" and "spatial skills" interchangeably throughout this article.

727

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939 FIGURE CAPTIONS

940 Figure 1. Item #2 of the training phase of the two-dimensional (2-D) mental rotation test used (EFAI-
941 E). Reprinted with permission from Santamaría et al. (2005). Copyright 2005 by TEA
942 Ediciones.

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944 Figure 2. Examples of slides from the MRTP, according to the characteristics of the stimuli used
945 throughout the three sessions: A) Concrete figures (i.e., stimuli that can be recognized by the
946 participants); B) and C) Abstract figures (i.e., those that follow geometrical patterns).

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948 Figure 3. Training phase in which the participant can observe the progressive rotation of the correct
949 stimuli (rotated) straight after they have given their response.

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951 Figure 4. Representation of the temporal sequence of events of the MR training with MRTP. ISI:
952 Interstimulus Interval.

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954 Figure 5. (a) Mean scores of the EFAI-E and the (b) EFAI-N in boys and girls by group for pre and
955 post measurements.

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964 Figure 1

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1029 Figure 4

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Table 1

Means and standard deviations for measures for the two phases in both groups.

Measure	Total (N = 81)			
	CG (n = 39)		EG (n = 42)	
	M	SD	M	SD
Raven (max. = 60)				
Pretest	29.41	9.47	30.62	10.55
Posttest	30.54	10.65	34.05	11.24
Increase	1.13	4.64	3.43	4.32
EFAI-E (max. = 30)				
Pretest	9.82	4.12	9.45	3.95
Posttest	13.62	5.32	16.21	5.51
Increase	3.79	4.56	6.76	5.03
EFAI-N (max. = 30)				
Pretest	13.1	6.87	14.02	7.21
Posttest	15.9	3.71	16.00	7.13
Increase	2.77	3.12	1.98	3.44

*Pairwise comparisons (mean difference).

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Table 2
Means and standard deviations for measures for the two phases and both sexes
in the CG.

Measure	Control group (N = 39)			
	Boys (n = 19)		Girls (n = 20)	
	M	SD	M	SD
Raven (max. = 60)				
Pretest	28.68	8.75	30.10	10.29
Posttest	30.53	10.80	30.55	10.78
Increase	1.84	4.65	0.45	4.64
EFAI-E (max. = 30)				
Pretest	10.79	4.86	8.90	3.11
Posttest	15.16	6.23	12.15	3.91
Increase	4.37	5.35	3.25	3.73
EFAI-N (max. = 30)				
Pretest	13.95	6.93	12.30	6.89
Posttest	16.68	6.86	15.10	6.66
Increase	2.74	3.09	2.80	3.24

*Pairwise comparisons (mean difference).

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Table 3
Means and standard deviations for measures for the two phases and both sexes
in the EG.

Measure	Experimental group (N = 42)			
	Boys (n = 18)		Girls (n = 24)	
	M	SD	M	SD
Raven (max. = 60)				
Pretest	28.67	11.23	32.08	10.0
Posttest	31.89	12.25	35.67	10.39
Increase	3.22	4.05	3.58	4.60
EFAI-E (max. = 30)				
Pretest	9.56	4.57	9.38	3.51
Posttest	17.94	5.73	14.92	5.06
Increase	8.39	5.35	5.54	4.51
EFAI-N (max. = 30)				
Pretest	14.44	7.93	13.71	6.78
Posttest	16.44	7.69	15.67	6.82
Increase	2.00	3.60	1.96	3.39

*Pairwise comparisons (mean difference).